

Text mining results are available as followed:

IBD:

<http://sourceforge.net/p/efo/code/HEAD/tree/trunk/src/efoassociations/ibd.tar.gz>

Autoimmunity:

<http://sourceforge.net/p/efo/code/HEAD/tree/trunk/src/efoassociations/immune.tar>

Skeletal disorders:

<http://sourceforge.net/p/efo/code/HEAD/tree/trunk/src/efoassociations/skeletal.tar>

Metabolism disorders:

<http://sourceforge.net/p/efo/code/HEAD/tree/trunk/src/efoassociations/metabolism.tar>